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RELAZIONE FINALE

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Titolo del Progetto	Groundwater dynamics and hydrological processes in Triveneto catchments: integrated data analysis, modeling, and experimental investigations
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1. Introduction

Mountain regions represent critical components of the global hydrological cycle, acting as natural water towers that regulate the availability and timing of freshwater resources for downstream ecosystems and human activities (Viviroli and Weingartner, 2004; Viviroli et al., 2007). In particular, alpine and pre-alpine catchments in northeastern Italy play a strategic role in sustaining river discharge, agricultural demands, hydropower production, and drinking water supply across densely populated lowland areas. Despite their importance, the hydrological functioning of these systems remains only partially understood due to their intrinsic complexity, strong spatial heterogeneity, and limited data availability.

Groundwater systems in alpine environments are especially challenging to characterize and model. They are controlled by highly variable geological settings, complex recharge mechanisms driven by snowmelt and precipitation, and dynamic interactions with surface water bodies such as streams and rivers (Winter, 1999). These interactions are further influenced by seasonal variability and extreme events, including droughts and intense precipitation episodes, which are expected to become more frequent and severe under ongoing climate change (IPCC, 2021). At the same time, increasing anthropogenic pressures—such as tourism, land-use changes, and the introduction of emerging contaminants—are adding new layers of complexity to the functioning and management of these fragile systems (Lapworth et al., 2012).

In this context, improving the understanding of groundwater dynamics and reducing predictive uncertainty in hydrological models represent key scientific and practical challenges. Traditional modeling approaches often rely on limited datasets and simplified assumptions, which may not adequately capture the coupled physical and chemical processes governing groundwater flow and solute transport in mountain environments. Recent advances in hydrology emphasize the importance of integrating multiple sources of information—including hydrological observations, hydrochemical data, and environmental tracers—to better constrain models and enhance their predictive capability (Kirchner, 2006; McDonnell et al., 2010).

Beyond quantity-related aspects, increasing attention is being directed toward water quality and contaminant dynamics in alpine environments. Hydrological variability, particularly during drought, can significantly influence solute concentrations by altering dilution, groundwater contributions, and flow pathways. At the same time, the occurrence of emerging contaminants introduces new challenges that require a deeper understanding of transport processes across multiple spatial scales.

The research activities presented in this report are framed within this evolving scientific perspective. The project aims to develop and apply innovative methodologies that combine field observations, laboratory experiments, and numerical modeling to investigate groundwater systems across multiple spatial and temporal scales. By adopting an interdisciplinary and multi-scale approach, the work seeks to bridge the gap between pore-scale transport mechanisms, aquifer-scale dynamics, and catchment-scale

hydrological responses, ultimately contributing to more robust and physically consistent predictions of hydrological and transport processes (Beven, 2012).

Specifically, the study focuses on alpine and pre-alpine catchments of northeastern Italy, where groundwater plays a fundamental role in regulating streamflow, controlling water quality, and buffering hydrological extremes. The research addresses several interconnected objectives:

1. improving the characterization and modeling of alpine aquifers leveraging several data sources;
2. analyzing the role of groundwater in controlling hydrological droughts and sustaining baseflow, as well as its influence on water quality dynamics;
3. investigating transport processes in heterogeneous porous media through controlled laboratory experiments, including the characterization of non-Fickian behavior (Berkowitz et al., 2006);
4. assessing the occurrence and transport of emerging contaminants in mountain environments subject to increasing anthropogenic pressure (Lapworth et al., 2012).

To achieve these goals, the project integrates complementary methodological approaches across multiple spatial scales. The analysis is primarily based on existing datasets, including piezometric, hydrometric, and hydrochemical observations, which are used to characterize groundwater dynamics, streamflow variability, and drought response. In particular, hydrochemical and water quality data are explicitly incorporated into the conceptualization and calibration of groundwater models, enabling improved process representation and a reduction of predictive uncertainty. Targeted field activities were conducted in the context of emerging contaminants, focusing specifically on the sampling and analysis of pharmaceuticals in selected alpine catchments. These campaigns provide novel information on the occurrence of contaminants in mountain environments and represent a key addition to the available datasets. These data-driven analyses are complemented by controlled laboratory experiments designed to investigate solute transport mechanisms in heterogeneous porous media. Using a novel experimental setup based on transparent hydrogel spheres and Planar Laser-Induced Fluorescence (PLIF), the experiments enable direct observation of concentration fields and the identification of non-Fickian transport processes at the mesoscale. Numerical and conceptual modeling approaches are then applied to integrate these different sources of information. This includes the development of groundwater flow models constrained by multiple data types, as well as the use of stochastic and interpretative models to analyze streamflow variability and drought dynamics. By combining these elements, the research contributes to advancing current understanding of groundwater systems in complex mountain settings. The integration of process-based knowledge across scales enables a more consistent representation of flow and transport phenomena, including contaminant behavior. Moreover, the proposed framework is flexible and transferable, making it applicable to other regions facing similar challenges.

Ultimately, the outcomes of this work aim to support more informed and integrated water resource management strategies, particularly in the context of climate change and increasing environmental

pressures. By improving the reliability of predictions related to groundwater dynamics, drought response, and contaminant transport, this research provides a scientific basis for the sustainable management of water resources in alpine environments (IPCC, 2021).

2. Main Activities and Results

2.1 Modeling of Alpine Aquifers

This activity focused on the investigation and numerical modeling of alpine aquifers, with particular reference to the Basso Chiese system, depicted in Figure 1. Alpine aquifers represent a key component of mountain hydrology, sustaining baseflow and downstream water availability, but their characterization is often complicated by complex geological settings, heterogeneous alluvial deposits, and strong interactions with surface water bodies.

Figure 1: Position of the Chiese Valley, affected by PFOS contamination phenomena.

The study builds upon a detailed hydrogeological conceptualization of the Basso Chiese aquifer, hosted in a thick alluvial sequence composed mainly of highly permeable gravels and sands, with an estimated thickness of 80–100 m or more in several areas. The aquifer is bounded laterally by mountain ranges with distinct lithological characteristics and receives recharge from multiple sources, including precipitation, lateral inflows from the valley sides, and significant exchanges with the Chiese River. The

latter plays a crucial role in the overall water balance, as confirmed by both piezometric observations and hydrochemical analyses.

To quantitatively describe these processes, an advanced modeling framework was developed, combining groundwater flow and solute transport simulations. The flow model was implemented using the MODFLOW-NWT code, while transport processes were simulated through a Lagrangian particle-tracking approach (random walk method), allowing for efficient representation of advective–dispersive mechanisms in a large and heterogeneous domain. The modeling domain was discretized into a three-dimensional grid composed of multiple layers, enabling the representation of vertical variability and groundwater circulation at different depths.

Figure 2: Transport model showing the trajectories obtained from the simulation using the optimal combination of parameters.

A key aspect of the approach is the integration of multiple data sources. The model incorporates piezometric measurements collected during several monitoring campaigns, hydrochemical data derived from field sampling and analysis (including Piper diagrams and ion ratios), and information on contaminant concentrations (PFOS) measured at selected monitoring points. Hydrochemical data proved particularly valuable for identifying recharge sources and flow paths, highlighting the contribution of both river infiltration and lateral inflows from the valley slopes .

The calibration of the model was carried out using a stochastic approach based on Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) techniques, which allowed for the systematic exploration of parameter uncertainty and the identification of optimal parameter combinations. This approach was essential to address equifinality issues, arising from the difficulty in uniquely separating the contributions of different recharge components, such as river leakage and lateral inflows .

Main results:

- Significant reduction of predictive uncertainty through the integration of heterogeneous datasets and the adoption of a probabilistic calibration framework.
- Improved estimation of key hydrological fluxes, including lateral groundwater inflows from valley slopes and stream–aquifer exchanges with the Chiese River, which are typically difficult to constrain.
- Identification of the main recharge mechanisms and flow pathways, supported by both hydraulic and hydrochemical evidence.
- Development of a flexible and transferable modeling methodology suitable for other alpine aquifers characterized by limited data availability and structural complexity.

Overall, the results highlight the importance of combining hydrological modeling with hydrochemical and tracer-based information to achieve a more reliable and physically consistent representation of groundwater systems. The proposed framework provides a robust basis for both scientific analysis and practical applications, such as the assessment of contamination risk, the delineation of capture zones, and the support of groundwater resource management in alpine environments.

2.2 Hydrological Drought Analysis

The response of alpine catchments to prolonged dry periods was investigated through the analysis of streamflow dynamics, with particular emphasis on recession behavior and its relationship with groundwater storage. The study focuses on the Brenta catchment, where long-term hydrometric and piezometric datasets allow for the characterization of hydrological variability under both wet and dry conditions.

The analysis of historical discharge data highlights a clear seasonal pattern, with higher flows typically occurring during late spring and autumn, while low-flow conditions are generally observed during summer and winter periods (see boxplots of monthly discharge in Figure 3). However, interannual variability is significant, and extreme conditions can substantially alter the typical hydrological regime.

Figure 3: Box plot of the Brenta River at Borgo Valsugana (left) and at Grigno (right), calculated from the historical time series, from 1990 to 2024 for Grigno and up to 2020 for Borgo Valsugana.

A detailed comparison between contrasting hydrological years—specifically 2014 (wet conditions) and 2022 (drought conditions)—provides key insights into system behavior. In 2014, abundant winter and early spring precipitation, combined with snow accumulation, resulted in sustained high flows throughout the year (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Year 2014 – top left: monthly precipitation; top right: discharge of the Grigno stream; bottom left: discharge of the Brenta River at Borgo Valsugana; bottom right: discharge of the Brenta River at Grigno. Red indicates discharge, and blue indicates precipitation.

In contrast, 2022 was characterized by a severe precipitation deficit, leading to markedly reduced streamflow, although the river maintained a non-negligible discharge even during prolonged dry periods (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Years 2014–2022 – top left: monthly precipitation; top right: discharge of the Grigno stream; bottom left: discharge of the Brenta River at Grigno. Red indicates discharge, and blue indicates precipitation (data for Borgo Valsugana are not available).

This behavior highlights the fundamental role of groundwater storage in buffering hydrological extremes. Even under severe drought conditions, the Brenta River exhibits a degree of resilience, maintaining baseflow through sustained groundwater contributions. This is further supported by the analysis of long-term water level data, which shows that groundwater systems respond more gradually and with a delayed reaction compared to surface water dynamics.

The relationship between precipitation, streamflow, and groundwater levels reveals that aquifer systems act as natural regulators of hydrological variability. Piezometric data indicate that groundwater levels

tend to respond to recharge events with a temporal lag and smoother dynamics compared to streamflow, reflecting storage-controlled processes. This delayed response is particularly evident during drought periods, when groundwater release sustains river discharge even in the absence of significant precipitation.

Additional insights are provided by the analysis of hydrochemical parameters, which show that during low-flow conditions, higher solute concentrations are often observed due to reduced dilution and increased groundwater contribution. In particular, the comparison between 2014 and 2022 highlights higher concentrations of several parameters (e.g., chlorides, sulfates, and electrical conductivity) during drought conditions, confirming the dominant role of groundwater in sustaining streamflow during these periods (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Comparison of mean parameters for 2014 and 2022 at Ponte Filippini for the Brenta River.

Main results:

- Identification of key hydrogeological controls on flow recession, including aquifer storage capacity and groundwater–surface water connectivity.
- Clear evidence that groundwater storage enhances drought resilience by sustaining baseflow during extended dry periods.
- Demonstration that streamflow dynamics are strongly influenced by delayed groundwater responses, leading to smoother and more persistent recession curves.
- Confirmation, through the analysis of the Brenta catchment, that groundwater contributions play a dominant role in maintaining streamflow under drought conditions.

A stochastic interpretative model is currently being applied to reproduce the observed variability in streamflow and groundwater dynamics. Preliminary results indicate that the model is capable of capturing both the temporal variability and the recession behavior of the system, supporting its use for the analysis of hydrological extremes and predictive assessments.

2.3 Transport Processes in Porous Media

The investigation of transport processes in porous media complements the field-scale analyses presented in Sections 2.1 and 2.2 by providing a process-based understanding of solute dynamics at smaller scales. While the modeling of alpine aquifers (Section 2.1) highlighted the importance of integrating hydrochemical information to reduce uncertainty, and the drought analysis (Section 2.2) emphasized the role of groundwater storage and delayed responses, these interpretations ultimately depend on the physical mechanisms governing flow and transport within heterogeneous porous systems. For this reason, controlled laboratory experiments were conducted to directly investigate these mechanisms.

The experiments were performed using a novel setup based on transparent hydrogel spheres and Planar Laser-Induced Fluorescence (PLIF), enabling high-resolution and non-invasive observation of solute transport processes. The hydrogel-based porous medium allows optical access to the internal structure while preserving key features of natural heterogeneity. A fluorescent tracer (Rhodamine WT) was injected into deionized water flowing through the system, and concentration fields were measured using PLIF techniques.

A series of experiments was carried out under controlled laminar flow conditions, with different interstitial velocities imposed to investigate velocity-dependent transport behavior. In particular, flow velocities on the order of 10^{-5} m/s were tested, allowing for comparison between different transport regimes. One experimental run was extended over several hours to capture late-time transport

dynamics and improve the characterization of breakthrough curves (BTCs), especially in their tailing behavior.

The experimental results provide direct insight into the mechanisms that, at larger scales, manifest as delayed responses and smoothing effects observed in groundwater systems. In particular, the presence of stagnation zones, recirculation regions, and preferential flow paths leads to non-uniform transport velocities and enhanced solute retention. These processes contribute to non-Fickian transport behavior, which is often observed in natural aquifers but difficult to quantify using field data alone.

The datasets obtained from these experiments were used to analyze solute dispersion, retention, and exchange processes within the porous medium. Forward and backward mass exchange coefficients were estimated, with the aim of linking transport behavior to flow conditions and establishing relationships with dimensionless parameters such as the Reynolds number. These results provide a quantitative basis for improving transport representations in larger-scale models.

Main results:

- Direct observation of concentration fields in heterogeneous porous media, enabling the identification of internal transport structures and flow patterns.
- Identification of non-Fickian transport mechanisms, including anomalous dispersion and long-tailed BTCs, associated with stagnation zones and recirculation processes.
- Experimental evidence that pore-scale heterogeneity leads to delayed solute release, consistent with the buffering and lag effects observed in groundwater systems at the catchment scale.
- Improved characterization of transport parameters, including mass exchange coefficients, supporting the development of more realistic transport models.
- Development of analytical and semi-analytical descriptions of transport in heterogeneous systems, informed by experimental observations.

Overall, these results provide a crucial link between pore-scale processes and field-scale behavior. The non-Fickian transport mechanisms identified in the laboratory help explain the delayed responses, mixing processes, and persistence of solutes observed in alpine aquifers (Section 2.1), as well as the sustained release of water and solutes during drought conditions (Section 2.2).

By integrating laboratory experiments with field observations and numerical modeling, the study adopts a multi-scale approach that enhances the physical consistency of groundwater models. This integration ultimately contributes to reducing predictive uncertainty and improving the representation of transport processes in complex mountain environments, with direct implications for water quality assessment and contaminant transport analysis.

2.4 Emerging Contaminants in Alpine Catchments

Building on the hydrogeological characterization (Section 2.1), the analysis of groundwater-driven hydrological processes (Section 2.2), and the investigation of transport mechanisms at the pore scale (Section 2.3), a field-based study was initiated to examine the occurrence and transport of emerging contaminants in alpine catchments. These contaminants, including pharmaceuticals and microplastics, represent an increasing environmental concern, particularly in mountain regions subject to strong seasonal tourism pressure.

As highlighted in Section 2.2, hydrological conditions—particularly during drought periods—have a significant influence on water quality, with reduced dilution and increased groundwater contribution leading to higher concentrations of dissolved constituents. This behavior suggests that hydrological variability plays a key role not only in water quantity but also in controlling contaminant dynamics. In this context, the investigation of emerging contaminants extends the analysis of water quality from conventional hydrochemical parameters to more complex and less studied pollutants.

Alpine environments are often considered relatively pristine; however, increasing anthropogenic pressures, such as tourism and associated wastewater production, can introduce contaminants into both surface water and groundwater systems. The hydrogeological characteristics of these catchments—such as high permeability deposits, strong groundwater–surface water connectivity, and the presence of preferential flow paths—can facilitate rapid transport and widespread distribution of contaminants, especially under variable hydrological conditions.

To investigate these processes, a multi-season monitoring strategy was implemented in selected alpine catchments, specifically in Val di Sole and Val di Fassa. These areas were chosen due to their high tourist pressure and their representativeness of alpine hydrogeological settings. The monitoring activities are carried out in collaboration with MUSE and Fondazione Edmund Mach, ensuring an interdisciplinary framework that integrates hydrology, hydrochemistry, and environmental analysis.

Sampling campaigns include the collection of water samples from both surface water and groundwater systems across different seasons, allowing the assessment of temporal variability and the influence of hydrological conditions on contaminant occurrence. This approach enables the identification of potential links between contaminant concentrations, groundwater contributions, and seasonal dynamics, such as those observed during low-flow periods.

The dataset collected through these campaigns represents a valuable basis for investigating the occurrence, variability, and transport pathways of emerging contaminants in mountain environments. In particular, the integration of these observations with the findings from Section 2.2 allows for the interpretation of contaminant dynamics in relation to hydrological controls, such as baseflow contributions and dilution effects.

Main results (ongoing):

- Implementation of a multi-season monitoring strategy, with three sampling campaigns completed, enabling the assessment of seasonal variability in contaminant occurrence.
- Collection of a novel dataset on emerging contaminants in alpine catchments, extending traditional water quality analysis to previously unmonitored compounds.
- Preliminary evidence of links between hydrological conditions (e.g., low-flow periods, groundwater dominance) and contaminant concentrations, consistent with patterns observed for conventional hydrochemical parameters.
- Establishment of the basis for a catchment-scale transport model, integrating field observations with the hydrological and transport processes identified in previous sections.

Although still ongoing, this activity represents a key step toward a comprehensive understanding of water quality dynamics in alpine systems. By explicitly linking contaminant occurrence to hydrological processes (Section 2.2) and transport mechanisms (Section 2.3), the study extends the project's multi-scale framework to include emerging environmental challenges.

This integrated perspective is essential for evaluating the vulnerability of alpine water resources to anthropogenic pressures and for supporting the development of effective monitoring and management strategies under changing climatic and socio-economic conditions.

3. Scientific Outputs and Dissemination

The research activities have produced **significant scientific outputs**, both in terms of methodological development and application to alpine hydrological systems.

Two main manuscripts synthesize the core findings:

- A manuscript currently under review demonstrates that **the integration of hydrochemical and water quality data into groundwater models significantly reduces predictive uncertainty**.
- A second manuscript, in preparation, focuses on **groundwater dynamics in alpine catchments**, with particular emphasis on the interaction between aquifers and surface water systems.

These works contribute to advancing current approaches to groundwater modeling by promoting a **multi-source data integration framework**, with clear implications for improving model reliability and supporting water resource management.

The results have been actively disseminated through participation in major international scientific conferences:

- At the **European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2025** (EGU25, Vienna, Austria, 27 April – 2 May 2025), the contribution “*Integrating hydrological data and hydrochemical data to reduce uncertainty in mountain aquifer modeling*” (EGU25-8088) was presented as a poster.
- At the **IAHS Scientific Assembly 2025** (Roorkee, India, 5–10 October 2025), the contribution “*Leveraging water quality data to reduce uncertainty in mountain aquifer modeling*” was also presented as a poster.

Participation in these conferences enabled:

- the dissemination of both **methodological innovations and applied results**,
- engagement with **the international hydrological research community**,
- and the collection of **valuable feedback** to refine ongoing research activities.

In addition, the research has fostered **interdisciplinary and institutional collaborations**, particularly with MUSE and Fondazione Edmund Mach, within the framework of field campaigns on emerging contaminants. These collaborations strengthen the link between experimental observations, chemical analyses, and modeling efforts, enhancing the overall impact and applicability of the research.

Overall, dissemination activities have contributed to:

- consolidating the international visibility of the research,
- positioning the work within current scientific discussions on groundwater resilience, uncertainty reduction, and climate change,
- and supporting the development of future collaborative research initiatives.

4. Conclusions

The research activities carried out have led to substantial progress in the understanding and modeling of groundwater systems in alpine and pre-alpine environments, addressing key challenges related to data scarcity, system complexity, and predictive uncertainty. By combining field observations, laboratory experiments, and numerical modeling, the project provides a comprehensive and integrated perspective on hydrological and transport processes in mountain catchments.

From a methodological standpoint, the work demonstrates that the integration of heterogeneous data sources—including piezometric, hydrochemical, and tracer data—represents a powerful approach to constrain groundwater models and significantly reduce predictive uncertainty. The application of this framework to alpine aquifers highlights its effectiveness in improving the estimation of key processes, such as recharge dynamics, lateral inflows, and groundwater–surface water exchanges, which are typically difficult to quantify in data-scarce environments.

The results also emphasize the central role of groundwater in regulating hydrological processes at the catchment scale. The analysis of streamflow dynamics and drought conditions shows that groundwater storage acts as a natural buffer, sustaining baseflow during prolonged dry periods and mitigating the effects of meteorological variability. At the same time, the observed relationships between hydrological conditions and water quality indicate that groundwater contributions strongly influence the concentration of dissolved constituents, particularly during low-flow periods when dilution is reduced.

A key advancement of this work lies in the adoption of a multi-scale approach to transport processes. Laboratory experiments conducted using PLIF techniques provided direct evidence of non-Fickian transport behavior, highlighting the importance of pore-scale heterogeneity, stagnation zones, and mass exchange processes in controlling solute dynamics. These findings offer a physical explanation for the delayed responses and mixing effects observed at the field scale, thereby strengthening the conceptual link between small-scale mechanisms and large-scale hydrological behavior.

This multi-scale perspective is further extended through the investigation of emerging contaminants in alpine catchments. The field-based monitoring activities demonstrate the growing relevance of water quality issues in mountain environments, particularly under increasing anthropogenic pressure. Preliminary results suggest that contaminant occurrence is closely linked to hydrological conditions, reinforcing the need to consider both flow dynamics and transport processes when assessing environmental risks. The integration of these observations with the hydrogeological and experimental findings provides a solid basis for the development of predictive models of contaminant transport at the catchment scale.

Overall, the project establishes a coherent and flexible research framework that connects data collection, process understanding, and predictive modeling across multiple spatial scales. This framework not only advances scientific knowledge but also provides practical tools to support water resource management, particularly in regions where groundwater plays a critical role for ecosystems, water supply, and environmental sustainability.

The outcomes of this work lay a strong foundation for future developments, including:

- the extension of modeling approaches to larger spatial scales and more complex hydrogeological systems;

- the incorporation of emerging contaminants into integrated groundwater and surface water modeling frameworks;
- the further development of multi-scale modeling approaches that explicitly link pore-scale processes to catchment-scale dynamics;
- the continued investigation of groundwater–surface water interactions under changing climatic conditions, with particular emphasis on drought frequency and intensity;
- the enhancement of monitoring strategies to better capture the coupling between hydrological variability and water quality dynamics.

In this context, the integration of experimental, field, and modeling approaches represents a key pathway for improving the reliability of predictions and supporting adaptive water management strategies in alpine regions facing increasing environmental and climatic pressures.

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